

THE CONCEPT OF BIOTECHNOLOGIES: DEFINITION, HISTORY, TYPES OF BIOTECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR PRACTICAL APPLICATION

¹R. Govindrao Dani, ²D.G. Sodikova

¹professor, ²(PhD)

Denau Institute for Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

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Abstract. *In this article, the modern risks of Biotechnology achievements and his philosophical throne has been considered. The emergence of Biotechnology is said to date back to ancient times. Humans have been unconsciously using biological processes since ancient times yogurt from milk, wheat and yeast, wine or vinegar from fruit juices those who came using the preparation technology. In addition, pedigree animals or even life processes based on the creation of quality plants varieties of humans lies in successful management by. So Biological Technologies they are somewhat naive views of Biotechnology, they are traditional called biotechnology.*

Keywords: *Biotechnology, science, progress, Factor, appearance, opinion, risk.*

Biotechnology is briefly a discipline that studies the possibilities of using living organisms and their systems in solving various technological problems, including the creation of living organisms with certain properties using genetic engineering.

Biotechnology is presented in the abstracts as a concept covering a wide range of procedures aimed at modifying living organisms in accordance with human goals.

For thousands of years, people have been using biotechnologies in agriculture, food production and medicine. The very term "biotechnology" was introduced by a Hungarian engineer named Karl Ereki. It happened in 1917.

The history of biotechnology. Early biotechnology allowed farmers to select and breed crops that produce the largest yields today: in sufficient quantities to support a growing population. As crops and fields became more and more voluminous, problems arose with their maintenance. Then it was discovered that individual organisms and their processed products quite effectively fertilize, restore nitrogen and fight pests. Throughout the development of agriculture, farmers inadvertently changed the genetics of crops, introducing them to new conditions and breeding them together with other plants. All these were the first forms of biotechnology [1].

Environmental biotechnology concerns science and applied knowledge related to the use of microorganisms and their products. Biotechnology combines fundamental knowledge in Microbiology, Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology, and engineering knowledge of specific processes and equipment. The main applications of Biotechnology in industrial hazardous waste treatment include: prevention of environmental pollution through waste treatment, restoration of polluted environments, and biomonitoring of environmental and treatment processes. A common biotechnological process in hazardous waste treatment is biotransformation or biodegradation of hazardous substances by microbial communities [3].

For a long time, people also used breeding in order to improve the production of crops and livestock, so that all this could then be eaten.

Selection was based on the fact that organisms with desirable characteristics were paired with the same organisms.

Practical application of biotechnologies. There are 4 large industrial areas in which biotechnology developments are actively used: Medicine, agriculture, chemical industry, rural industry

Biotechnologies are also used to recycle and process waste, clean areas contaminated by industrial activity (this is called bioremediation), and create biological weapons[2].

Biotechnologies in agriculture have caused the emergence of genetically modified crops. These are biotechnological crops - plants used in agriculture, whose DNA has been modified using genetic engineering methods.

Such food crops are resistant to certain pests, diseases, stressful environmental conditions, and resistance to various chemical treatments.

Seed production biotechnology

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